

OpenStreetMap, beyond just Data: The Academic Track at State of the Map 2022

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OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a project and a community, or community of communities [1], geared towards producing a free, editable, and global geographic database to which anyone can contribute. With more than 8.8 million registered users contributing more than 7.8 billion data points as of 8 August 2022 [2], it has attracted attention across various spheres, from tech giants [1], through governmental organizations and NGOs [3,4], popular media [5], social activists [6], to the academic world [7–9]. The latter is reflected not only in a large corpus of scientific publications relating to OSM, but also in the establishment of the *OSM-science* mailing list [10], dedicated to correspondence on academic studies of OSM, and since 2018 – in the inclusion of a dedicated Academic Track in the annual State of the Map (SotM) conference, the global meeting of the OSM community [11]. The proceedings of the Academic Track at the SotM 2022 conference, taking place in Florence, Italy on August 19-21, 2022 [12], include 19 short papers corresponding to 9 talks and 10 lightning talks presented at the conference. These talks join 49 talks from the previous 4 Academic Track editions as an example of the continued interest of the scientific community in OSM.

The study of OSM is a study of a research object that keeps on evolving and changing [13]. This opens for multiple ways to approach it. However, a classification of recent OSM-related publications [7] shows that some ways are more dominant than others, with the vast majority of papers following data-centric approaches. Unsurprisingly, this theme is also evident in some of the studies included in these proceedings. Several abstracts present domain-specific applications of OSM data, combining OSM data to derive public urban green spaces [14], plan sustainable transport infrastructures [15], map detailed floor plans from digital building models into OSM and back out [16], and using OSM to

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understand global urban green accessibility [17]. Other studies explore the potential for integrating OSM data with other data sources, e.g. combining OSM water tags with Water Point Data Exchange (WPdx) to improve the mapping of rural water infrastructures in Africa [18], or working towards a knowledge-graph (i.e. Wikidata) integrated OSM dataset [19]. Analyses of data quality are not absent here with Herfort et al. [20] assessing OSM building completeness in urban areas across the world, Camboim et al. [21] investigating the impact of grid cell size for OSM data quality analysis, and Dickinson et al. [22] assessing OSM data quality regarding network navigability in areas where high levels of corporate contributions were observed. A final group of abstracts emphasizes data accessibility, either by supporting mapping activities or data analysis: Anderson & Omidire's [23] development of the Analysis-Ready Daylight OSM Distribution makes global OSM data analysis easier and faster; Vestena et al. [24] introduce a new open-source QGIS Plugin named "OSM Sidewalkreator" to help the OSM community to better draw the geometries of sidewalks, crossings, and kerbs in an automatic manner; Schott et al. [25] proposed a workflow to enhance multi-label remote sensing image classification by automatically extracting OSM multi-label training data and verifying them via a feedback-loop in the Tasking Manager projects.

Yet, as noted above, OSM is not just a database - it is the cumulative result of the actions of individuals, organizations, and communities, all being a fundamental part of what OSM is. Hence, OSM is also a social product in which interpersonal, organizational, and behavioral dynamics play a pivotal role [26]. The implication of this is that OSM is a system that extends beyond itself with flows of inputs, people, and resources coming from other systems into it and back out. This social perspective, while existing in the literature, had historically received much less attention [7]. Surveying the abstracts included in these proceedings suggests that the tide may be turning, with 7 of the abstracts detailing research that is socially-oriented in one of several ways. First, 3 abstracts present applications of OSM data that are specifically geared towards social causes, exploring the potential of participatory mapping using a dedicated mobile app based on OSM for promoting geo-literacy among high-school students [27], for analyzing the accessibility of urban spaces for the visually impaired thus prompting equal mobility and walkability in the city [28], or for mapping vulnerable spaces such as refugee camps, using open drone imagery collected as part of the activities of the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) [29]. Generally, humanitarian efforts within OSM, such as in the last example, seem to induce more socially-oriented research, as seen in Solís' exploration of the way the YouthMappers movement within OSM uses universities as hybrid organizations to navigate between global humanitarian efforts and students' local motivations [30], or Steele's anthropological study of OSM [31] (probably the first since Lin's pioneering work [32]) that uncovers the above mentioned flows through the notion of 'supply chains'. The work of Shrestha et al. [33] joins the one about YouthMappers mentioned above in studying effects on participants by showcasing that mapping skills training of recent high-school graduates and undergraduate students have long-term benefits for youth. Finally, Juhász and Mooney [34] shine a unique light on social dynamics by exploring the meaning for OSM of null island, the fictitious place located at the origin of the WGS1984 coordinate system to which much data is erroneously allocated.

The differentiation made here between data-oriented and social research is not meant to suggest that one is better or more required than the other. This differentiation may not even be real or beneficial given the extent to which contribution processes and data are

interlaced [35] and the awareness of many authors to the social side of OSM, sometimes through direct interactions [7]. Hence, the growing attention to the social aspect of OSM is a positive sign showing that the scientific endeavor termed as OSM science [36] is further developing and maturing. But it also shows that it still has room to grow, promoting interdisciplinary collaborations between researchers that can comprehensively consider both the data and the social aspects of OSM. We use this editorial as an open call for researchers to pursue this direction, further enhancing our understanding of OSM.

References

- [1] Anderson, J., Sarkar, D., & Palen, S. (2019). Corporate editors in the evolving landscape of OpenStreetMap. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 8(5), 232.
- [2] OSM Contributors (2022). OpenStreetMap Stats. Retrieved from https://planet.openstreetmap.org/statistics/data_stats.html
- [3] Haklay, M., Antoniou, V., Basiouka, S., Soden, R., & Mooney, P. (2014). Crowdsourced geographic information use in government. *Report to Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (World Bank)*, London.
- [4] Minghini, M., Kotsev, A., & Lutz, M. (2019). Comparing INSPIRE and OpenStreetMap data: how to make the most out of the two worlds. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XLII-4/W14, 167–174.
- [5] Elliott, V. (2022). Ukrainians are scrubbing open-source maps to keep intel from Russia's army. *Rest of the World*. Retrieved from <https://restofworld.org/2022/ukrainians-osint-maps-russia>
- [6] Quinn, S., & Yapa, L. (2016). OpenStreetMap and food security: A case study in the city of Philadelphia. *The Professional Geographer*, 68(2), 271–280.
- [7] Grinberger, A. Y., Minghini, M., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., & Mooney, P. (2022). Bridges and barriers: An exploration of engagements of the research community with the OpenStreetMap community. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(1), 54.
- [8] Sehra, S.S., Singh, J., & Rai, H.S. (2017). Using Latent Semantic Analysis to Identify Research Trends in OpenStreetMap. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 6(7), 195.
- [9] Yan, Y., Feng, C.-C., Huang, W., Fan, H., Wang, Y.-C., & Zipf, A. (2020). Volunteered Geographic Information Research in the First Decade: A Narrative Review of Selected Journal Articles in GIScience. *International Journal of Geographic Information Science*, 2020, 34(9), 1765–1791.
- [10] OSM Science mailing list: Discuss Anything Science Related in the OpenStreetMap Ecosystem. Retrieved from <https://lists.openstreetmap.org/listinfo/science>
- [11] State of the Map 2018, Academic Track: Call for abstracts. Retrieved from <https://2018.stateofthemap.org/academictrack>
- [12] State of the Map 2022. Retrieved from <https://2022.stateofthemap.org>
- [13] Grinberger, A. Y., Anderson, J., Mooney, P., Ludwig, C., & Minghini, M. (2021). OpenStreetMap as a multifaceted research subject: the Academic Track at State of the Map 2021. In: Minghini, M., Ludwig, C., Anderson, J., Mooney, P., & Grinberger, A.Y. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at the State of the Map 2021 Online Conference, July 9-11 2021*, 1–5.
- [14] Rieche, T., & Hecht, R. (2022). Automated derivation of public urban green spaces via activity-related barriers using OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [15] Timaite, G., Hulse, J., & Lovelace, R. (2022). OSM for sustainable transport planning. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [16] Tauscher, H., Krishnakumar, S., & Heigener, D. (2022). Floor plan extraction from digital building models. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.

- [17] Battiston, A., & Schifanella, R. (2022). Understanding and modelling accessibility to public green in large urban centers using OpenStreetMap data. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [18] Nakacwa, S., McCusker, B., Sill, K., Clark, C., & Nealon, R. (2022). Combining Volunteered Geographic Information and WPdx standards to Improve Mapping of Rural Water Infrastructure in Uganda. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [19] Dsoua, A., Schott, M., & Lautenbach, S. (2022). Comparative Integration Potential Analyses of OSM and Wikidata – The Case Study of Railway Stations. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [20] Herfort, B., Lautenbach, S., Porto de Albuquerque, J., Anderson, J., & Zipf, A. (2022). Inequalities in the completeness of OpenStreetMap buildings in urban centers. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [21] Camboim, S.P., Paiva, C., Schmidt, M., Elias, E., Bortolini, E., & Neivas, G. (2022). The cell size issue in OpenStreetMap data quality parameter analyses: an interpolation-based approach. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [22] Dickinson, C., Patel, J., & Sarkar, D. (2022). Corporate editing and its impact on network navigability within OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [23] Anderson, J., & Omidire, T.W. (2022). Increasing OSM Data Accessibility with the Analysis-Ready Daylight Distribution of OSM: Demonstration of Cloud-Based Assessments of Global Building Completeness. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [24] Vestena, K., Camboim, S., & Santos, D. (2022). OSM Sidewalkreator - A QGIS plugin for automated sidewalk drawing for OSM. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [25] Schott, M., Zell, A., Lautenbach, S., Demir, B., & Zipf, A. (2022). Returning the favor - Leveraging quality insights of OpenStreetMap-based land-use/land-cover multi-label modeling to the community. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [26] Grinberger, A.Y., Schott, M., Raifer, M., & Zipf, A. (2021). An analysis of the spatial and temporal distribution of large-scale data production events in OpenStreetMap. *Transactions in GIS*, 25(2), 622–641.
- [27] Lan, D., Dalyot, S. & Baram-Tsabari, A. (2022). Landmarks for accessible space – promoting geo-literacy through geospatial citizen science. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [28] Cohen, A., Natapo, A., & Dalyot, S. (2022). Leveraging OpenStreetMap to investigate urban accessibility and safety of visually impaired pedestrians. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [29] Chan, C.Y.-C., Weigand, M., Alnajar, E.A., & Taubenböck, H. (2022). Investigating the capability of UAV imagery for AI-assisted mapping of Refugee Camps in East Africa. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.

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- [30] Solís, P. (2022). YouthMappers: A Hybrid Movement Design for the OpenStreetMap Community of Communities. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [31] Steele, A.L. (2022). Mapping crises, communities and capitalism on OpenStreetMap: situating humanitarian mapping in the (open source) mapping supply chain. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [32] Lin, Y.-W. (2010). A qualitative enquiry into OpenStreetMap making. *New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia*, 17(1), 53–71.
- [33] Shrestha, A., Raj Budhathoki, N., & Erbstein, N. (2022). OpenStreetMap as a tool for skill building. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [34] Juhász, L., & Mooney, P. (2022). Null Island - a node of contention in OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Liu, P., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., & Juhász, L. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022*, Florence, Italy, 19-21 August, 2022.
- [35] Sieber, R.E., & Haklay, M. (2015). The epistemology(s) of volunteered geographic information: a critique. In: *Geo: Geography and Environment*, 2(2), 122–136.
- [36] Grinberger, A.Y., Minghini, M., Juhász, L., Yeboah, G., & Mooney, P. (2022). OSM Science - the academic study of the OpenStreetMap project, data, contributions, community, and applications. In: *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(4), 230.